

Gender Action Plan

WE ARE HBP stands for “Work for and Engage in Activities and Research for Equality in HBP”

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Figure 1: Members of the HBP Gender Advisory Committee (GAC)

As of 1 Jan 2019. The GAC Chair is Svenja CASPERS and the GAC Co-Chairs are Andrew DAVISON & Benjamin WEYERS.

Project Number:	785907	Project Title:	Human Brain Project SGA2
Document Title:	Gender Action Plan for SGA2		
Document Filename:	D11.2.10 (D69.10 D131) SGA2 M7 SUBMITTED 190401.docx		
Deliverable Number:	SGA2 D11.2.10 (D69.10, D131)		
Deliverable Type:	Report		
Work Package(s):	WP11.2		
Dissemination Level:	PU = Public		
Planned Delivery Date:	SGA2 M7 / 31 Oct 2018		
Actual Delivery Date:	SGA2 M12 / 01 Apr 2019		
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SciTechCoord Review:	N/A		
Editorial Review:	Birgit SCHAFFHAUSER, Guy WILLIS (EPFL, P1)		
Description in GA:	The Gender Action Plan is a required reference document to align structure and processes, objectives and key activities for improved gender equality in HBP with the DIR, SIB, GAC, Ethics Advisory Board, Education Programme and Subprojects.		
Abstract:	The Gender Action Plan identifies key measures for SGA2 to enhance equal opportunities and a better gender balance for the HBP. It is based on a proposal by convelop, the preliminary considerations of EAF Berlin during SGA1, feedback from the HBP Directorate and suggestions by the HBP Gender Advisory Committee.		
Keywords:	Gender, Diversity, Equal Opportunities, Action Plan, Logic Chart		
Target Users/Readers:	HBP Community, EC		

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1. Executive Summary

The HBP Gender Action Plan (GAP) will support improving gender balance in the HBP via education, information and encouragement. Firstly, the positive effects of an improved gender balance on excellence, innovation and collaboration will be communicated. To raise awareness of its beneficial effects in terms of both fairness and also scientific outcomes is considered an important motivational factor.

In order to inspire positive change, to encourage and motivate HBP members, the GAP:

- Starts with a vision for the HBP. A vision naturally goes well beyond the current practice. It invites to reflect the current situation and future possibilities for activities.
- Aims to remind HBP leaders of their responsibilities. Their contributions are crucial to improve of the gender balance.

Within this framework, the GAP presents the action as a coordination Task, which is responsible for making suggestions, contributing to meetings, delivering concepts and training accordingly. This is expressed in the logic chart below.

Based on the call for proposals, Task T11.2.5 (Coordination of Gender Equality Activities) includes five Specific Aims (see Figure 2 and Section 3). A Logic Chart will provide indicators for input (resources contributed to this GAP, derived measurable activities the coordination Task will deliver), output (expected measurable effects on follow-up actions by boards, leaders and staff) and outcomes (long term effects and related KPIs which depend on several internal and external factors, see appendix). The logic chart or Input-Output-Outcome-Chain (see Table 1) thereby comprises the contributions of the coordination Task, as well as the contributions of HBP managers and leaders crucial for implementation and actual changes. It will support the monitoring and discussion of strategy implementation with the DIR, SIB, SP Leaders and Managers.

Figure 2: Specific Aims

These Specific Aims for this GAP were derived from an analysis carried out by EAF Berlin during SGA1¹, followed by a call for proposals for SGA2 with predefined aims. These aims will be carried out in alignment with the overall project strategy as defined by the Directorate and include: strengthening the leadership culture, structure, and process; supporting work-life organisation and equality in scientific careers; implementing gender at conferences, in education, and workshops;

¹ A summary was made public as [HBP_Gender_Survey_Flyer](#) (EAF Berlin, Results of the gender survey may / June 2017)

raising awareness and disseminating good practices; and measuring and reporting on Gender Equality Activities.

These objectives will be achieved through implementation of the Gender Action Plan which includes coordinating activities with the Gender Advisory Committee (GAC), dissemination at HBP events, mainstreaming sex and gender in HBP research, governance, and processes, bolstering leadership structures and supporting career development.

In collaboration with members of SP12 and the GAC, T11.2.5 will support direct communication and facilitate these efforts by providing change management expertise, virtual community building, workshops and coaching. These activities will be reflexively developed in response to project needs and the results of case studies, surveys, and self-evaluations.

2. Vision

As a European Union Flagship Project, the HBP has to meet high expectations and drive beyond state-of-the-art research. It will demonstrate how equality can be fostered by a network of outstanding researchers cooperating throughout Europe. The HBP is well suited to serve as a best practice example, especially for remote, distributed and complex partnerships, of how to build momentum for equality, to inspire positive change and pave the way for European leadership in the next generation of science.

The HBP intends to initiate a new WE ARE HBP culture that will not only focus on scientific excellence, but will also progressively raise attention on how to increase fairness. This new culture will engage men and women from different scientific disciplines, countries and research institutions (whereas most previous approaches to increase a better gender balance engaged mainly women). Intersectional equality refers to the fact that variables do not exist separately but must be considered together; such as being non-native English speaking and having a different educational and cultural background.

WE ARE HBP stands for “Work for and Engage in Activities and Research for Equality in HBP”. It communicates the following vision to motivate HBP leaders:

Figure 3: Motivational Vision for the HBP

The vision indicates that this “Gender Action Plan” is based on a broader understanding of leadership and equality issues in science; namely, on the intersectionality of gender with other variables, based on an inter-categorical approach: The ideal image of a brain researcher still has a strong male bias. The linking of specific expertise with gender leads to intersections, thereby reinforcing stereotyping (see also Section 6.1 below) In addition, the socio-economic environment plays an important role: Depending on their family background and obligations, nationality and culture, researchers at the

beginning of their career are more or less familiar with expectations and norms in the scientific environment (social capital), which influences their interactions within the HBP. Each dimension can be effective on its own or interact with other dimensions and reinforce exclusion mechanisms.

An anti-categorical approach has been chosen for motivation and open dialogues to reflect conceptions openly, such as the process of construction of gender. WE ARE HBP aims to avoid stereotypes and to encourage open discussions, valuing different opinions, sharing advice, experiences and challenges.

The main activities are driven by engagement and co-creation (for further explanation, see Section 6.1 below).

The underlying assumption and requirement for such a coordinating activity is that HBP members can be motivated to justify their Flagship position by evolving a pioneering responsible leadership approach for “excellence and innovation by diversity and collaboration” (see also Appendix:).

3. Logical Framework and Specific Aims

The Gender Action Plan is based on preliminary considerations developed by EAF Berlin (SGA1)², the SGA2 call for proposals in the gender field and the selected proposal of convelop, and addresses all aspects of the call:

- 1) **Strengthen leadership culture, structure and processes**
- 2) **Support work-life organisation and equality in scientific careers**
- 3) **Implement “gender at conferences, in education and workshops”**
- 4) **Raise awareness and disseminate good practices**
- 5) **Measure and report on Gender Equality Activities**

Structurally, responsibilities for the GAP are defined as “gender coordination task” within SP11/PCO. Measures and indicators in this GAP were outlined in accordance with the given role, while motivating and reminding governance bodies of their responsibilities.

The measures outlined in further detail in this document refer to what a coordination Task can deliver, based on the resources and the background analyses available. Activities and measures of the GAP, their feasibility and prioritisation will be constantly reported by the “gender coordination task” and reflected in the light of actual development, in close collaboration with the Gender Advisory Committee (GAC).

Given the structural positioning of a coordination Task within this complex, large scale project, the GAP is indeed ambitious.

While all governance bodies and personnel are expected to follow the GAP to the best of their ability, one must keep in mind that, for the time being, the HBP is less an organisation and more a network-based project bringing together many organisations which differ widely in their culture, practices and regional framework conditions. The HBP is changing to become a new legal entity, reconfiguring not only scientific priorities but the overall partnership.

The specific aims of the call were set into a logical framework and further developed based on feedback from the HBP Directorate and suggestions by the HBP Gender Advisory Committee:

² The report comprises figures about the gender distribution in leadership positions as well as leverage points for improvements and derived measures (like mentoring, guidelines, a proposed further gender conference etc., see introduction to this Gender Action Plan). A summary was made public as “HBP Gender Survey Flyer”, see Fn. 1;

3.1 Vision and Communication

Aim 1) Strengthen the leadership culture

- Develop and communicate a vision for the HBP, raise awareness.
- Contribute to meetings on a regular basis: actively present gender good practices, encourage change.

Aim 4) Raise awareness and disseminate good practices

- Prepare messages addressing equal opportunities and contribute to HBP internal media.
- Contribute to external media, collaborate with initiatives and networks for dissemination.

Aim 5) Measure and report on Gender Equality Activities

- Report on activities, interim and final results of the GAP, involve the HBP in further steps, encourage active contributions.

3.2 Structures and Processes

- Expand the Gender Advisory Committee (GAC) and the community of change contributors.
- Raise awareness for resources and support available at partner universities and institutions.
- Analyse structures and procedures relevant for equal opportunities and reporting, deliver guidelines and advice, based on the SGA1 Report (see also: [HBP Gender Survey Flyer](#)).

3.3 Research and Lectures

Aim 3) Implement gender at HBP conferences, in education and workshops

- Ensure that gender and diversity are discussed at HBP conferences.
- Develop and deliver related programmes, concepts and incentives (gender and diversity of topics, speakers, participants).

3.4 Individuals, Teams, Leaders

Aim 2) support work work-life organisation and equality in scientific careers

- Develop and deliver concepts and incentives encouraging leadership and mutual support for career development and work-life balance.
- Raise awareness for unconscious biases, offer leadership guidance and advice.

4. Measures for Intervention

The GAP will build on two key types of measures for intervention:

- 1) Guidelines supporting the mainstreaming of equality as quality criteria in all key areas, which can be distributed and accompanied with training and coaching opportunities.
- 2) Incentives to implement the guidelines and encourage further improvements, which are directly related to the needs of research and research management.

The overall logic of intervention is summarised in the WE ARE HBP logic chart (see Table 1: Input-Output-Outcome (Logic Chart) for WE ARE HBP. It links T11.2.5's inputs with the activities of HBP

leaders, as the latter are needed to implement the measures and deliver the expected long-term outcomes.

4.1 Mainstreaming Equality as Quality Criteria in HBP Documents and Guidelines

The HBP, as a European Flagship Project, distributes guidelines within the partnership, especially for organising conferences and writing and reviewing proposals. Introducing guiding questions and criteria on equal opportunities in all relevant documents is an important measure for raising awareness. Following the recommended criteria in decision-making processes is key for improving equal opportunities. Due to the cross-cutting character of equality issues, documents and guidelines are related to a variety of different tasks and procedures as outlined in Table 1.

4.2 Incentives to Foster Equal Opportunities

The HBP has committed itself to consider gender and diversity as important aspects of research topics, as well as to increase the proportion of female scientists in leadership positions, and among early career researchers, PhD students and postdocs. However, the benefits of including a gender dimension in research and striving for equal opportunities in teams and leadership positions are not known to all contributors. Additionally, for a complex, network-based project of remote partners working under different framework conditions, suitable measures must first be developed (see also appendix). Measures will build further on improvements achieved during SGA1 and derived aims for this Gender Action Plan, e.g. anchoring and composition of the GAC, introducing gender related topics at HBP conferences.

It is therefore important to communicate positive outcomes regarding HBP science that touches on sex and gender, to highlight success stories in leadership representation, and to offer incentives for further improvements. Therefore, T11.2.5 will communicate and encourage the implementation of:

- Incentives will be developed during SGA2 These incentives will open the opportunity to apply for dedicated budgets (e.g. publication costs, travel costs and site visits, training opportunities, facilitation of workshops dedicated to improving teamwork and collaboration).
- Outstanding results and actions related to the gender dimension will be emphasised with honorary awards, e.g. for best papers addressing gender as variable in research content, best conferences with best gender balance in speakers and participants, or equal opportunities for all genders in teams, as important aspects of leadership responsibilities and to formally recognise the value of the result to the HBP.

Award winners will receive a certificate, either at HBP Summits or in SP Meetings. They can opt to have their profile displayed on the HBP website and in the HBP Newsletter. Their outstanding achievements will be brought to the attention of HBP Boards and the European Commission.

A summary of all incentives is given below in Table 2.

Table 1: Input-Output-Outcome (Logic Chart) for WE ARE HBP

Area of Intervention	Inputs: Support provided by the Gender Coordination Task T11.2.5	Outputs: Activities of HBP Boards, Leaders and Staff, supported by Task T11.2.5	Long-term Outcomes: Achieved by long-term commitment and persistence
Vision, Communication for Equality in the HBP	Communicating a vision for the HBP: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributions in meetings Messages addressing equal opportunities as crosscutting issue relevant for quality & excellence Report on gender equality activities Disseminate results via newsletters, platforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invitations for T11.2.5 to contribute, discussion & integration of equality issues. Leading to visibility of relevance of equal opportunities for HBP. Measured by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keywords in agenda items & protocols addressing action steps Number of related messages from DIR, SIB or PCO. 	Gender-aware leadership: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rising awareness of relevance & importance of gender equality & diversity Rising commitment across different Subprojects & functions.
Structures and Processes	Guidelines for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appointment procedures Recruitment & promotion of employees Call for proposals (gender balance & RRI as selection criteria) Resource List: Advice & help on data collection, reporting, publication tracking, career development questionnaires.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usage, distribution of guidelines Encouragement of target groups Leading to improved quality & transparency. Measured by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keywords in protocols, e-mails Monitoring & reporting on gender balance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved quality & transparency Shift towards gender & diversity balance in boards, leadership positions, workgroups.
Research and Lectures	Guidelines for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity as research topic Diversity of participants (lectures) Diversity at conferences: topics, speakers, participants Advice & concepts for best papers, lectures, conferences Workshops & training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of incentives: Budget & procedures for best practices Encouragement & participation of target groups Leading to visibility of best practices in enhancing equal opportunities. Measured by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reports, numbers of publications, lectures & speakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved gender & diversity balance of contributors Gender, diversity as innovative research content.
Individuals, Teams, Leaders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidelines for: Leadership & teamwork, high potential mentoring, peer groups. Advice & concepts for: HBP leadership best practices, High Potential Programme, Peer groups. Advice & coaching on a regular basis, via short, virtual meetings, webinars, e-mails. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of special programmes & organisational support Announcement, encouragement & participation Leading to visibility of fairness & equal opportunities. Measured by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reporting, Monitoring, Coordination support, Responses to career development questionnaires. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved work-life balance & commitment Mutual support across diverse groups & roles Shared "WE ARE HBP" culture. Shift towards better gender & diversity balance within HBP, especially equality in scientific careers.

Table 2: Awards, Incentives and Calls

Categories	Best Paper	Best Conference	Best Leadership	High-Potential Programme
Rational and Objectives	Improved visibility of papers considering sex, gender and other diversity factors as research content	Improved visibility of conferences considering sex, gender and other diversity factors in content, speakers and participants ³	Improved managerial practices focusing on equal opportunities in science and management of science	Career development of researchers at the beginning of their scientific career & scientific managers
Quantities	3 awards per SGA (SGA2, SGA3)	1 conference per year	3 awards per SGA	SGA2: 3 awards SGA3: Support for 25 researchers and scientific managers per year
Target groups	Researchers at the beginning of their scientific career	Conference organisers	Leaders of Subprojects and workgroups	SGA2: Supervisors SGA3: Researchers at the beginning of their career, scientific managers, supervisors and mentors
Selection⁴	Award jury defined by the GAC	Directorate or jury	Directorate or jury	Jury defined by the GAC
Honorary Awards in SGA2	For new insights, research framework considering "diversity research" in	For best gender balance among speakers, and/or for addressing gender-related topics	For best measures to improve team diversity and culture, fair task distribution (first focus: gender balance)	For leaders who support career development of high-potential young researchers (first focus: gender balance)
Calls in SGA3 Incentives, financial resources dedicated solely to scientific purposes	Travel costs to present the paper at conferences, for publication costs	Costs for outstanding speakers, diversity of participants, proceedings (gender or diversity focus)	Cost for training, facilitation of e.g. team-building workshops, side visits	Travel costs and accommodation for site visits; costs for training or coaching of high-potential young researchers and scientific managers)
Financial Resources	To be defined for SGA3			
Organisational support provided by T11.2.5	Organising and advertising the calls, communication with jury, event (HBP Summit)			

Note: Details to be defined in collaboration with GAC, SIB and DIR; changes to incentives programme possible

³ Conferences might not only strive for a good balance according to "sex count" of speakers and participants. Additionally, they might address e.g. accessibility for people with disabilities, child care options that consider possibly different age and cultural background of children, presentations addressing gender and other diversity factors (e.g. sex in animal studies, gender, age and socio-economic background of participants in medical studies).

⁴ The selection processes will be aligned to the addressed topic (science, conference organisation, leadership and career development) and target groups.

5. Work Plan and Action Steps

The T11.2.5 workflow for SGA2 distinguishes 3 phases, which are outlined in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Overview on Project Phases

Note: The top row indicates the month in the calendar year, the second the HBP SGA2 project month.

The three phases overlap:

- 1) The Setup Phase guarantees a better understanding, time needed to set up appropriate working structures, procedures and first developments. Measures and planned activities will be aligned with expectations and readiness of DIR, SIB and GAC (see also Appendix:).
- 2) The Development Phase will deliver detailed concepts.
- 3) The Implementation Phase will overlap with the development phase, contributing already in parallel to meetings, conferences, trainings etc., while still elaborating further guidelines and reports.

As outlined in Table 1 above, T11.2.5 delivers input with the intent to raise awareness, activate and motivate both HBP leaders and community. The intended outputs and related measures are also clearly outlined in column 2 of the table. Expected long-term outcomes are also indicated.

Table 3 summarises the related milestones and deliverables, followed by further details on which action will be undertaken and measured by T11.2.5.

Table 3: Milestones and Deliverable

Milestone	Description	Month
MS11.2.8	Report on the approach and options for implementation for career mentoring and peer groups	M12
MS11.2.9	Handbook with guidelines provided for PCO, SP leaders, Education Programme, comprising recommendations, examples and best practices.	M18
Deliverable	Description	Month
D11.2.10	The Gender Action Plan is a required reference document to align structure and processes, objectives and key activities for improved gender equality in HBP with DIR, SIB, GAC, Ethic Board, Education Programme and Subprojects.	M7

5.1 Vision, Communication for Equality in the HBP

5.1.1 *Contribute Regularly in Meetings*

T11.2.5 will contribute with short impulses (5-10 minutes) at Board and Project meetings and cooperate specifically with the GAC, the HBP Education Programme, the HBP Innovation Team, SP12 and the Ethics Advisory Board (see also below, structure and processes, which were defined in the setup phase of the GAP).

Direct communication with and the strategic involvement of the DIR are key for T11.2.5, to remind the HBP community of the importance of the gender subject, as professional and scientific obligations entail a risk of scientists/leaders of losing attention and control in this respect. Frequent communication and sharing of leadership experiences, combined with state-of-the-art information, hands-on checklists and advice should help to strengthen the HBP's leadership culture with regard to raising gender equality.

The activities will start with setup phase and be measured by:

- 2 meetings / month (DIR, SIB, PCO, SP11 and/or other SPs) on average

5.1.2 *Raise Awareness and Disseminate Good Practices*

T11.2.5 will contribute to the HBP virtual platforms and usage of already established virtual infrastructure, like "collaboratories" and forums, newsletters, the public website and social media channels. Board members and scientists will be encouraged to contribute as role models, offering their research and experience, through a short description of best practice examples regarding gender and equality. Visibility of equality issues as part of existing contributions to media will be encouraged by suggesting measures such as adequate tagging.

T11.2.5 will cooperate with other initiatives and networks of the European Commission (e.g. GenPORT, GEAR). By presenting the results of the gender equality activities in the HBP; for example, at conferences within this context (e.g. European conference on Gender Equality in Higher Education, the Gender Summit); a high disseminator effect can be achieved.

The activities will start latest development and be measured by:

- A minimum of one contribution / month (news, blogs, etc.) on average

5.2 Structure and Processes

Due to the complexity of the HBP as a network with different layers, partners and interests, T11.2.5 will define strategic issues with the DIR and the GAC. T11.2.5 strongly depends on support provided by the Project Coordination Office /SP11. The PCO supports the DIR in setting gender equality on their agenda, integrates the GAP in collaborative tools, webpage and social media, in meetings and conferences, and provides data for KPI monitoring, for example, via "the Blue Book" internal directory, as well as other publications related to gender and diversity.

5.2.1 *Management and communication processes for GAP implementation*

Structure, Roles and Processes are defined as follows

5.2.1.1 Directorate (DIR)

- Sets the strategy, reinforces communication about the vision and objectives, decides on priorities
- Releases official gender and diversity relevant PR content, reports and results for dissemination

5.2.1.2 Gender Advisory Committee (GAC):

The GAC is an advisory body to the DIR of the HBP and the PCO. The GAC contributes to the alignment and transfer of the Gender Action Plan into governance structures and the subprojects. It is the GAC members' role to:

- provide advice and feedback on the Gender Action Plan as a whole as well as on the implementation of specific gender and equality activities (as planned in the Gender Action Plan).
- announce and promote activities within their subproject / area and initiate activities of their own.

The GAC is preferably gender balanced and should represent the governance structure of the HBP. Its members are board members, leaders, scientists, technologists or managers; for details see appendix.

5.2.1.3 T11.2.5 Coordination of Gender Equality Activities

T11.2.5 communicates with the DIR, GAC, Subprojects and other groups as follows:

- 1) DIR: communication reports, strategic decisions on process design and key activities, such as recruiting procedures.
- 2) GAC: preparing measures and activities as well as reports for discussion with the GAC.
- 3) Subprojects (SPs): contributing to meetings and monitoring, clarifying implementation of specific measures and activities. The contributions will depend on the expertise, scientific goals and tasks of the SPs, in relation to gender equality and diversity:
 - a) SP1 to SP10: provide guidelines, interact in meetings to encourage consideration of sex, gender and diversity aspects in research design and publications. Raise awareness of the relevance of sex, gender and diversity aspects and foster an open discussion within and between SPs on these topics.
 - b) SP11: contribution to quality control, guidelines and lectures.
 - c) SP12: close collaboration, to support all efforts of SP12 aiming to address issues of sex and gender within the HBP (RRI includes gender equality).
- 4) Specific Target Groups: tailoring activities, offering training and advice (e.g. for SP Managers, SP Leaders, group leaders, early career researchers, etc.).
- 5) Education Programme: contributing with workshops, guidelines.

5.2.2 Resource List

T11.2.5 will develop and provide a Resource List, including measures and services available at HBP partner universities; including dual career support, leadership training, general mentoring. The best practice examples gathered in SGA1 will be further expanded during SGA2.

Additionally, networks and communities of female researchers will be added to the Resource List for reference in conference guidelines (e.g. <https://anneslist.net/> for female systems neuroscientists, <https://500womenscientists.org/request-a-scientist> across the globe, various fields: <http://www.academia-net.org/> leading Women Scientists).

The aim of the Resource List is to make HBP leaders aware of the support they can rely on at their universities, but also to raise awareness of best practice examples being implemented in other institutions, projects or even single working groups. This will help to achieve better gender equality, improve work-life balance, support talented scientists, recruit the best candidates or similar.

The Resource List currently contains details from at least 15 universities and partner institutions and will be continuously updated.

The activities will start in the setup phase, will continue and distributed in the development phase, measured by:

- Introducing one university or partner institution per month (news, blogs etc.) on average, in alignment with the given resources.

SGA1 Resource Information

Most research organisations and universities have implemented a variety of equality measures, like awards and guidelines for appointment committees, leadership trainings, mentoring systems, especially to encourage female scientists and support their career development efforts. EAF Berlin collected best practice examples of HBP Partner institutions in SGA1, which can be viewed on the HBP public website at <https://www.humanbrainproject.eu/en/about/gender-equality/gender-activities-best-practice-interviews/gender-activities-best-practice-interviews-full/>. Excellent summaries on best practice examples and scientific background have been provided by research projects and initiatives of leading universities, like the League of European Research Universities (LERU). Some LERU universities are also HBP Partners.

5.2.3 Analysis, Guidelines, Advice and Collaboration

T11.2.5 will analyse guiding documents like the governance handbook, conference guidelines, SOPs, Calls for Expression of Interest, with a view to helping them to integrate gender mainstreaming. Guidelines for selection procedures for boards, work groups and promotion practices will also be developed.

The activities will start in setup phase and continue in the development phase. They will be measured by the distribution of:

- A minimum of three revised HBP internal handbooks and procedures
- A minimum of two guidelines (for boards, work groups, etc.).

Background

Governance structures and procedures can enhance or hinder the participation of women in decision making and leadership. Given the complexity of the HBP, it is important to ensure that partners, and leaders at different organisational levels are aware of the clear commitment of the HBP as a European Flagship Project to enhance equal opportunities. They also need to be given clear guidance on how to support this aim in everyday routines and decision making.

5.3 Research and Lectures

5.3.1 Gender at HBP Conferences, in Education and Workshops

T11.2.5 will be present at HBP conferences with workshops and other actions to raise awareness on equality issues. Actions to be prepared include mini surveys or polls (using mentimeter, feedbackr, slido, etc.) on topics such as team composition, task distributions or diversity aspects in research. They can be answered via mobile phones and results can be presented on conference screens, followed by background information and directions for activities.

T11.2.5 will become acquainted with existing conference and quality guidelines, and either contribute to their further development or complement them by providing stand-alone materials, such as:

- Introductory quick check list,
- Promotion and communication of a conference or event, including the search for invited presentations and key-note speakers (seek male and female speakers, gender sensitive presentation and research topics, support colleagues with child care responsibilities or special needs),
- Options for formats and conference designs that foster communication and diverse contributions,
- List of possible add-on workshops and interventions to raise awareness on equality issues and scientific leadership.

T11.2.5 will encourage researchers to make gender-related research results visible in publications and at conferences (The “Gender Balance in HBP” section in the Framework Partnership Agreement emphasises the willingness of HBP to “pay special attention to sex and gender”, specifically in SP2: Human Brain Organisation and SP8: Medical Informatics Platform”).

Additionally, a best conference and best paper award will be considered, to draw special attention to outstanding research frameworks and methods on sex, gender, age or other diversity aspects of brain research. Incentives might also be offered, such as conference proceedings, travel costs for outstanding speakers (see Table 2: Awards, Incentives and Calls above).

5.3.2 Guidelines for Diversity & Gender in Education

T11.2.5 closely collaborates with the Education Programme. Existing guidelines will be analysed to identify where sex, gender and diversity are a particularly relevant issue, such as guidelines for applications of conferences and participants. Advice will be provided on how to integrate and communicate these aspects.

Guidelines for gender and diversity issues in education and training will be provided. By addressing equality and diversity as cross-cutting issue of science and the management of science, lecturers will be encouraged to emphasise sex and gender aspects in their science accordingly. The guidelines include exercises and offer advice on how to encourage male and female participants to contribute in different activities, e.g. take different roles in group work.

T11.2.5 will provide workshops at student conferences, followed by webinars and peer groups to reach a broader community (see above).

The activities will start in the development phase and be measured by:

- A minimum of three guidelines: for lecturers, for researchers, for organisers and reviewers,
- A minimum of three “Gender at conferences” per year,
- A minimum of one concept for selection and incentives “best conferences”, “best papers”, etc.

5.4 Individuals, Teams, Leaders

5.4.1 *Guidelines and Support for Leaders, Teams, Individuals*

T11.2.5 will provide guidelines, tailor-made for HBP leaders. A first set of guidelines will focus on recruitment strategies, equal opportunities and work-life balance in the career development of HBP staff. This is supposed to start a dialogue within the HBP, followed by offering a virtual leadership “*jour fixe*” to provide further support, according to demand.

T11.2.5 will explore opportunities to introduce a “Leadership *Jour Fixe*” (no more than 20-30 minutes, via video conference or webinar) to ensure regular meetings, thus raising awareness of the topic and nurturing the expertise on equality issues in the HBP. T2.11.5 will report on *jour fixe* topics and provide advice on identified issues, existing questions and practical challenges.

5.4.2 *Incentives and Support for Leadership Best Practices*

T11.2.5 will develop incentives and present them to the SIB and DIR for further implementation.

The incentives programme supports and honours HBP leaders, who want to achieve a better gender and diversity balance in their teams and enhance equal opportunities in career development of team members. Their exemplary leadership efforts are of high relevance for the HBP.

An open call in SGA3 will give the opportunity to request a budget dedicated for trainings, coaching, facilitation of team building workshops or side visits focusing on work-life balance, equal opportunities in career development (see Table 2 above; programme still to be defined in detail for SGA3).

In SGA2, best practice examples will be nominated to receive an honorary award. Award winners will receive a certificate, have their profile displayed on HBP website and will be presented to HBP boards and the European commission, emphasizing the importance of their activities or achievements for the HBP.

5.4.3 *Mentoring*

T11.2.5 will produce a list of General Mentoring Programmes and Dual Career Services provided by partner universities and research institutions. It will also follow up on the proposal by EAF Berlin in the preliminary version of the Gender Action Plan developed during SGA1 to offer mentoring. Indeed, providing mentoring was suggested and defined as requirement for the call of gender coordination proposal for SGA2. The GAP includes two suitable approaches as outlined below.

5.4.3.1 *The HBP High-Potential Programme*

The “HBP High-Potential Programme” is planned to be implemented to provide cross-organisational, virtual mentoring support for mentees, with a focus on improving or defining career opportunities in the fields of research defined by Subprojects. A call will be developed by T11.2.5 to apply for specific funding, in order to give interested Subprojects, the opportunity to receive a budget for side visits, training and coaching opportunities for high potentials (see Table 2 above). Subprojects will be supported in their search for suitable collaborations and mentors by T11.2.5.

Mentoring in the HBP should benefit scientists/managers in this complex project, characterised by spatial remoteness of involved partners. It will focus on strategic (personal) decisions and/or further career steps of scientists and managers alike, either in related industries or as interdisciplinary approach within HBP.

5.4.3.2 Peer Mentoring

T11.2.5 will also explain peer mentoring systems to students, the education programme, Subproject managers and leaders. Peer mentoring fosters mutual support among peers, supports the development of networks and an equality-oriented culture among scientific and administrative staff. Mutual support in teams reduces the workload of key scientists and team leaders. Again, T11.2.5 will present guidelines and advice to support the empowerment of the peer groups towards self-organisation.

Peer mentoring takes place between 2 persons or a group of persons. At least one person (peer mentor) has specific experiences and is willing to share these experiences. The peer mentee(s) are interested to discuss and learn from these experiences, e.g. on how to deal with work-life issues and family obligations, on strategic career planning.

The composition of the peer groups will depend on topics and interests of the target groups. A specific target group are female scientists to foster their career development.

The mentoring and peer mentoring group activities are thereby strongly linked to the leadership guidelines and the accompanying regular meetings on leadership issues.

The activities will start in the development phase and be measured by:

- One concept for mentoring, peer groups and related incentives,
- A minimum of one guideline for leaders, and one guideline for mentors and peer groups,
- A minimum of four related coaching meetings, with a minimum of 30 participants in total,
- One concept for leadership incentives.

Appendix:

Gender and Diversity for the HBP: Definitions and Rationale

Equal Opportunities, Gender Mainstreaming and Diversity Management are cross-cutting issues, which enhance innovation capacity. However, diversity can also lead to underperformance, so special attention and supportive measures are needed to foster mutual understanding and effective collaboration⁵, especially in projects characterised by complexity, such as the HBP, which involves a large number of remote partners.

Diversity: The HBP will clearly focus on improving the gender balance and equal opportunities. Sex and Gender are two aspects of diversity. Basic diversity dimensions protected by European law against discrimination are: sex, age, sexual orientation, disabilities, race and ethnicity, religion and beliefs. Gender often intersects with other aspects, influencing how a person is perceived and enabled to contribute and develop within a community. Intersecting aspects are basic dimensions such as educational background, culture, role and position within an organisation or project. The unique capabilities and experiences of a person lead, amongst others, to unique perceptions, heuristics and problem-solving strategies, often referred to as “cognitive diversity”, enhancing intellectual excellence and the innovation capacity of a team, project or organisation^{6 7}.

Introducing the term “diversity” into the HBP aims to:

- 1) raise awareness for the intersectionality of the subject,
- 2) the proven relation with scientific outcomes and innovation, and
- 3) to clearly demonstrate that measures will be designed for the benefit of all, to invite all HBP leaders and staff to contribute⁸, as well as
- 4) to draw attention to the fact that, in order to engage a broader community of scientists and especially for public engagement as emphasised in the framework of the HBP’s RRI activities, one needs to consider the diversity of different stakeholders.

As a European Flagship project, the HBP faces a very specific set of challenges and conditions:

- It is a large international project consortium, distributed throughout Europe, with additional partners in the USA, Japan, and China, which currently comprises more than 125 partners. It is challenged by the following characteristics:
 - Partner organisations, leaders and staff of the temporary Project represent heterogeneous organisations and contribute according to their organisational and individual scientific (career) interests. Only for the lifetime of the Project, members are also part of the overall HBP organisational structure, shared vision and culture.
 - Remote, distributed communities are split into Subprojects with limited resources to meet face to face and to contribute to generic Project aims.
 - Subprojects have defined their own Objectives and Deliverables, which are more or less aligned with the “gender equality aims” of the overall Project⁹.

⁵ DiStefano J. & Maznevski M.L. 2000: Creating value with diverse teams in global management. *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 29, No.1, pp. 45-63

⁶ Hong L. and Page Sc. E. (2004): Groups of diverse problem solvers can outperform groups of high-ability problem solvers, *PNAS* November 16, 2004 101 (46) 16385-16389;

⁷ Page Sc. E. (2017): *How Great Teams Pay Off in the Knowledge Economy*, Princeton University Press.

⁸ Stewart A. & Valian V. (2018): *An Inclusive Academy. Achieving Diversity and Excellence*, MIT Press.

⁹ Cooke, N. J., & Hilton, M. L. 2015: *Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science*. Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press

- Any organisational and/or culture change will meet with resistance. Change management theory and practice has established models and processes that support successful change. However, these models and processes might be insufficient for temporary, distributed organisations.

As a “rule of thumb” in change management, the probability of success can be estimated as follows (see: Cady St. H., Jacobs R., Koller R. (2014): The Change Formula. Myth, Legend, or Lore?):

$$D \times V \times S > R$$

Dissatisfaction (D) multiplied with the Vision (V) multiplied with first Steps (S) must exceed Resistance (R). In this context, “Multiply” has more symbolic character, demonstrating that if only one of the three aspects is missing, the overall value will be zero.

- Dissatisfaction in companies often arises from outside pressure like diminishing profits, changes in markets or customer behaviour. For funded research projects and the gender dimension this means that there must be clear evidence that funding will depend on an adequate gender balance and/or on how gender is addressed in research context. Adequate means, that actual numbers of male and female PIs in a specific field of science should be considered. In science, juries for funding proposal and peer reviews of research outcomes affect the direction and level of dissatisfaction. Ratings and feedback for further improvements should therefore include the gender balance of teams as well as gender and diversity in research content.
- Vision refers to the necessity of a shared vision what can be achieved by striving for change
- First Steps are concrete steps that the organisation is sure it will be able to undertake towards the vision
- Resistance depends on previous experiences, perceptions (in this case often of terminologies like “gender balance”, “gender conferences” etc.), fear to lose status etc. but also on the number of changes forced on an organisation at the same time. Resistance is foreseen as crucial factor within the HBP which is currently changing towards becoming a new legal entity, reconfiguring not only scientific priorities but also the overall partnership.
Resistance based on the perception of equality initiatives and efforts has proven to be especially strong. Unfortunately, rather than coping with and reducing this resistance, communication strategies and affirmative action often even contribute to it, by generating stereotypes and outgroups. These activities can even have negative effects, as studies have shown¹⁰.
- Especially in STEMM sciences and project like the HBP, where scientific leadership by women is still underrepresented, an inclusive culture can only be successfully fostered by ensuring that all sexes/genders are addressed and motivated in a balanced way, and that intersectional and diversity thinking is taken into consideration.
- The HBP approach “includes” and mainstreams gender equality by demonstrating its benefit in research and education. In this context, the HBP referred to Londa Schiebinger, who emphasises that affirmative measures should avoid, amongst others, the assumptions that “all women or all men are the same” or that “differences between women and men hold across cultures”¹¹. We have established successful short checklists for “diversity in research” as well as “diversity in education”.

¹⁰ Kalev A., Dobbin F., Kelly E. 2016: Best Practices or Best Guesses? Assessing the Efficacy of Corporate Affirmative Action and Diversity Policies. *American Sociological Review*, Vol 71, Issue 4, pp.589-617

¹¹ Schiebinger, L. 2014: Gendered innovations: harnessing the creative power of sex and gender analysis to discover new ideas and develop new technologies; *Triple Helix* 2014, 1:9 <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s40604-014-0009-7>, obtained: 17.8.2017

- Success factors for organisational change efforts, especially when cultural change is required, and values, norms and perceptions are challenged, have been subject of research and practice over the last 50 years. Due to the rising complexity of global organizations and projects, well established processes like Kotter's "Eight Step Process for Leading Change"^{12 13}, have been further improved¹⁴ to not only build a shared vision connected with institutional strategies as well as powerful coalitions with directorates and advisory boards¹⁵, but also to constantly seek opportunities for activities involving as many members of an organisation as possible, addressing their needs and offering quick wins as stepping stones for further development. Building self-sufficient networks of supportive change agents is crucial, especially for large projects that can be considered "distributed temporary organizations", because best practices of stable organisations, with spatial proximity cannot be easily applied here¹⁶.

¹² Kotter, J. 2007: Leading Change. Why transformation efforts fail. HBR, Jan, pp.96-103;

¹³ Burnes B. 2005. Complexity theories and organizational change IJMR, V. 7, issue 2, pp.73-90

¹⁴ Kotter J. 2014: Accelerate, HBR Press, Chiva R. et.al. 2014: Organizational Learning, Innovation and Internationalization. A Complex System Model, BJM Vol. 25, Issue 4, pp.687-705

¹⁵ Cacace M. et al. 2015. Structural Transformation to Achieve Gender Equality in Science. Guidelines. Deliverable D.8.3. of the STAGES project, funded by FP7/2007-2013, http://www.stages.unimi.it/upload/documents/Guidelines_STAGES_new.pdf, obtained: 17.8.2017

¹⁶ Martinsuo M. and Hoverfaelt P. 2017: Change program management: Toward a capability for managing value-oriented, integrated multi-project change in its context International Journal of Project Management, Vol 35, Issue 7

GAC Terms of Reference (ToR) and communication with the DIR

Terms of Reference for the Gender Advisory Committee (GAC)

1. Purpose/Function of the GAC:

1.1 The GAC is an advisory body to the DIR of the HBP and the PCO. The GAC contributes to the alignment and transfer of the Gender Action Plan into governance structures and the Subprojects.

1.2. It is the GAC members' role to:

- provide advice and feedback on the Gender Action Plan as a whole.
- provide advice and feedback on the implementation of specific gender and equality activities (as planned in the Gender Action Plan).
- announce and promote activities within their Subproject / area.
- initiate activities of their own.

In the various SPs, the GAC is supported by the assigned team and Task leader, responsible for "coordinating gender equality activities".

2. Membership in the GAC

2.1. The GAC is preferably gender balanced and should represent the governance structure of the HBP. Its members come from different domains and have various functions within the HBP (Board members, leaders, scientists, technologists or managers). Specifically, the following HBP bodies are represented:

- All Subprojects (maximum 2 members per SP; one male, one female)
- Student representatives (maximum 2 members; one male, one female)
- Ethics Advisory Board (EAB) (1 member, if no EAB representative is among the SP-nominated members)
- Science and Infrastructure Board (SIB) (1 member, if no SIB representative is among the SP-nominated members)
- Directorate (1 member)
- Project Coordination Office (1 member)

2.2. Each Subproject and the HBP students appoint preferably two members (a man and a woman), who will take turns in a balanced way. If not covered by those members, the EAB and SIB will appoint one additional member for the GAC, respectively. One member of the DIR and one member of the PCO ensure a close link and communication with the strategic and management levels responsible for gender equality in HBP.

2.3. Members of the GAC are appointed for two years (or until the end of each SGA, respectively).

2.4. The GAC may consult other experts on an *ad hoc* basis.

3. Leadership of the Gender Advisory Committee

3.1. The GAC has two co-chairs, who represent the GAC to the HBP and external bodies. The GAC will elect its chairs from among its members. The tenure of the chairs is until the end of each SGA.

4. Working Principles of the GAC

4.1. The GAC uses a mailing list to communicate all information relevant to its members. All information, minutes and results will also be stored and made accessible for the GAC by the responsible task leader and will be accessible for further funding periods of the HBP.

4.2. Consultation by the GAC proceeds as follows:

- Each GAC member can introduce initiatives and ideas for discussion.
 - Material that requires feedback is provided online (usually by the responsible task leaders, but inputs might also come from GAC members). Such inputs include, for instance, the specific implementation concept for an activity, or documents such as guidelines and reports that have been prepared by the responsible Task team T11.2.5.
 - Each GAC member decides within a week whether this input is of interest and relevance to the domain they represent, and whether they want to provide feedback and engage in the discussion.
 - Feedback can then be provided in writing or verbally within a month via online surveys or email to the Task leader. The feedback differentiates major concerns and suggestions for improvement.
 - Based on the feedback provided by the GAC, the responsible Task leader will revise the material in close contact with GAC members until all “major concerns” are clarified.
 - Finally, the GAC decides on the adoption of the final version by majority vote (majority of the votes cast; Subprojects and students (both with 2 representatives each in the GAC, have one vote each).
 - The GAC members support the communication of the documents, measures and activities that have been adopted in their area of responsibility.
- 4.3. The GAC Chairs will have a teleconference with the task leader on a quarterly basis.
- 4.4. The GAC will have at least one physical meeting per year.
- Meetings are scheduled by the task leader in consultation with the GAC Chairs.
 - The agenda will be shared with GAC members at least 1 week prior to the meeting.
 - Preparation and follow up of the meeting will be undertaken by the responsible task leader in consultation with the PCO and the GAC Chairs.

5. Declaration of interests

5.1. GAC members must declare potential conflicts of interest through the HBP conflict of interest registry. When issues are discussed that may involve a conflict of interest, the affected members shall recuse themselves from the discussion. Conflicts of interest can be reported in oral or written form and should be noted in the minutes of the relevant meeting.

6. Review schedule

6.1. These Terms of Reference will be reviewed by the GAC for each SGA. They can also be reviewed at any given time upon request by a member of the GAC.